

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GEBREMICHAEL****FIRST NAME: SHEWAYIREF****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. The Technic of Academic Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-14)
2. Punctuation Marks and their Usage (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American and British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Writing Style Guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING – THE EUCLID UNIVERSITY WAY

1) INTRODUCTION

First, I am excited about the course material and thank the authors for their contribution. I discovered through the course that English writing is, in fact, the foundation of a student's education before starting the path to the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.). Furthermore, I prepare for future courses via the ACA-401D course pack. However, learning a language is a lifelong rather than a one-time course. In 2023, I plan to continue working toward getting a higher degree and mastering effective English communication. The course helps to advance my understanding of Standard English writing and other subject-matter courses, preparing me for the Ph.D. course and thesis work.

The ACA-401D period one course pack taught me various things, including how to write essays effectively, structure them, use punctuation marks correctly, recognize the variations between American and British English, avoid plagiarism, and use writing style guides. In addition, I make notes from the course on how I will apply proper English writing to quizzes, major papers, and response papers.

In this response paper, I emphasize the five fundamental principles of English writing that I learned from the ACA-401D course material for period one and the tutorial video. These are writing structure, Plagiarism, punctuation usage, the difference between American and British English, and the use of writing style guides.

2) THE TECHNIC OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

In this section, I aim to provide an overview of the basics of essay writing, an understanding of the steps for writing a good essay, and the basic rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2021, 6–14). Academic writing incorporates research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork that may or may not be publishable in journals, books, newspapers, manuscripts, theses, dissertations, or other forms (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Academic essays have a process of problem definition, resource gathering, critical thinking and reading, essay planning, and essay writing. As a result, the fundamental academic essay writing techniques are as follows: early start-up, defining the question and analyzing the task, and drafting an initial plan (EUCLID 2021, 7).

The fundamental procedures for writing an essay begin broadly and become more specific as they progress. Ideas are essential when writing an essay. One must critically read and think to extract meaningful information from credible academic sources. An academic essay includes careful reading, analysis, comparison and contrast, persuasion, conciseness, clarity, and exposition (Purdue University, n.d.). The inspiration for those essays came from reading about the subject in question. The conscious application of established techniques to the processing of gathered information is what critical thinking entails. The identified information needs organization into a plan or structure. As a result, they were underlining and making notes while reading to help write an effective essay.

The introduction, body, and conclusion are the three primary sections of the essay's structure. Most frequently, paragraphs make up an essay's body. Each paragraph covers a single primary concept (EUCLID 2021, 11). The topic sentence of a paragraph will introduce the main idea, followed by supporting phrases to clarify and develop the statement. Sentences providing assistance and giving analysis followed.

The steps involved in writing an essay are referencing, editing, and submitting it. A paper presentation is a formal type of presentation. The general rule in essay writing is to start early, stay focused, write clearly, and avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 13). Starting early in the writing process, sentence planning, critical thinking on the question, and constant draft revision all contribute to effective essay writing.

3) PUNCTUATION MARKS AND THEIR USAGE

Punctuation marks are symbols that separate phrases and sentence fragments and clarify their meanings. One of the significant rules for written communication is the proper use of punctuation. How we currently punctuate sentences restricts the definition of the

concept we want to convey. The ACA-401D coursepack one presented the different punctuation marks and how to use them in written English language communication. Little punctuation marks are preferred in sentences because they do not change the meaning. Punctuation gives our work a silent intonation. We can halt, stop, stress, or pose a question using a comma, period, exclamation point, or question mark. Writing becomes more precise and clear when appropriate use of punctuation because it allows meaningful information to transfer.

Apostrophes, brackets (round, square, curly, and angled), bullet points, colons, semicolons, commas, dashes, hyphens, full stops, question marks, exclamation points, and quote marks are among the several types of punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 14–23). One needs to be aware of how to use them properly. Changes vary the way of expressing an idea in punctuation. For example, putting an apostrophe before or after "s" changes the concept. The second indicates plural, while the first suggests ownership.

Appropriate using punctuation marks improve the essay's quality and increases the argument's clarity.

4) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

Knowing the differences and use of American and British English is advantageous in and of itself (Purdue University, n.d.; Academia, n.d.). The existence of global mass media and media technologies, as well as differences in population density, national wealth, higher education attainment levels, and political and economic standing worldwide, all contribute to linguistic diversity. Because of these circumstances, American English predominated over British English (EUCLID 2021, 25).

Learning the importance of understanding American and British English variations in terms of usage, pronunciation, spelling, meaning, grammar, and syntax is very advantageous. Also, whether taking or learning English in another formal setting, we must stick to only one of the two varieties rather than mixing them.

5) PLAGIARISM

Academic Plagiarism is using another's work without acknowledging or crediting the original author. Presenting someone else's ideas or work as own, with or without that person's consent, by incorporating it into own work without giving it due credit is known as "plagiarism." The definition applies to all published and unpublished works, whether in manuscript, print, or electronic form (University of Oxford, n.d.). Avoiding plagiarism with proper citation is the best solution (EUCLID 2021, 34). Two types of citations are available: in-text citations and lists of works cited as a reference.

Plagiarism can occur when paraphrasing someone else's work without citing the source. In this case, one has yet to translate the original text into other words ultimately

and has attempted to deceive the reader by turning the order backward. The words that appear in the original text should be highlighted (University of Guelph, n.d.).

Therefore, students or academic writers should avoid academic plagiarism and proper citation of others' work in academic essay writing.

6) WRITING STYLE GUIDES

Writing styles provide structure to a piece of paper, whether it is for academic or business purposes. The ability to adhere to a standard and good English writing style determines the writer's quality.

The general writing guidelines, which help to write standard English in academic or business writing, are fundamental concepts. Writing style guidelines cover different aspects: sentence length, the layout of the manuscript, spelling usage (US versus UK), use of abbreviations and symbols, structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, and use of headings and lists (EUCLID 2021, 41-42). These guidelines assist the writer in learning how to use and write academic or business writing.

In most colleges and universities in Ethiopia, the American Psychological Association (APA) style guide is the most preferred style for writing academic essays. The APA emphasizes the need to speak about everyone respectfully and inclusively. When writing under APA Style, authors must utilize language devoid of prejudice and refrain from supporting divisive ideologies or denigrating attitudes. Practicing proofreading work for a correction, one has learned to examine the writing for syntax, wording, and spelling errors (American Psychological Association, n.d.).

7) CONCLUSION

Academic essays are frequently given as homework or as part of class assignments, and they may be both rewarding and challenging types of writing. An academic essay is a condensed writing assignment that calls for a variety of comprehension abilities from the student. It includes careful reading, analysis, comparison and contrast, persuasion, conciseness, clarity, and exposition. An academic essay's primary goal is to motivate students to write about ideas and concepts using nothing more than their ideas as a guide. An academic essay paper must be brief, have a precise aim and direction, follow the structure, be original, have the correct citations and punctuation, and follow the style manual. It must also be thoughtful and fascinating.

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